

STUDY OF THE SPECIFIC ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY OF NEW DERIVATIVES OF MULTI-LIGAND BIOACTIVE COORDINATION COMPOUNDS BASED ON DICLOFENAC

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353411>

Abstract: *The article studied the specific anti-inflammatory activity, acute toxicity and accumulation of samples of new complex compounds synthesized on the basis of diclofenac, which are supposed to have increased bioavailability and reduced toxicity. The study of the specific anti-inflammatory activity of new diclofenac-based complexes showed that diclofenac, metal complexes (Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+}) based on it had antiexudative activity similar in its effectiveness. According to the results obtained, these metal complexes exhibit an anti-inflammatory effect, which decreases in the following order: Dicl-Ni-EDA > Dicl-Zn-EDA > H-Dicl > Dicl-Cu-EDA. The formation of the Dicl-Ni-EDA complex makes it possible to enhance anti-inflammatory activity.*

Keywords: *anti-inflammatory activity, complex, compounds, diclofenac, antiexudative activity, drugs, biological properties.*

JOURNAL OF PUBLIC PEDAGOGIES

ISSN 2207-4422

IMPAKT FAKTOR: 7.455

Introduction. Metal complexes of pharmaceutical ingredients are increasingly attracting the attention of scientists from different countries due to increased activity, dose reduction and other useful aspects. Compared with free ligands, metal complexes exhibit some other biological properties, which will be improved in future studies. In addition, due to complexation, the permeability of drugs into the cell through the membrane increases. These claims have been repeatedly proven for many medicines, including in the case of diclofenac (Dicl) [1–6].

The Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been working for a long time to study the biological, in particular anti-inflammatory, activity of synthesized mixed diclofenac/ethylenediamine (EDA) ligand complexes with some d-metals using the equimolar ratio of Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} acetate salts and ligands [7]. Inflammation is a complex local nonspecific protective reaction of the body against the effects of pathogenic harmful factors (physical, chemical, biological) that perform functions such as protecting the body from foreign bodies or cleaning it from decomposed own cells. Anti-inflammatory drugs by their nature

are steroid and nonsteroidal. Nonsteroidal drugs, in turn, are divided into two groups: phenylacetic acid derivatives and sulfoanilide drugs.

Diclofenac (Dicl) is a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug from a number of phenylacetic acid derivatives. It is usually used as a medicine in the form of sodium salt. Originally discovered in 1966, it was used in the treatment of rheumatological diseases. By 1988, it ranked 8th in a number of medical products used in more than 120 countries. Diclofenac is included in the list of vital medicines. But experts suggest introducing a ban due to an increase in the number of heart attacks (~40%) and other cardiovascular diseases as a result of its long-term use.

The aims of this research is to study the specific anti-inflammatory activity, acute toxicity and accumulation of samples of new complex compounds synthesized on the basis of diclofenac, which are supposed to have increased bioavailability and reduced toxicity.

Materials and methods. The obtained complexes were tested for their anti-inflammatory activity using carrageenin models. For the initial screening of anti-inflammatory activity, a classic carrageenin model was used. The experiments were carried out on rats (in the

amount of 40 pcs.) of both sexes weighing 160 ± 20 g. The animals were divided into 9 groups: a control group and 8 experimental ones, each with 5 animals. Inflammation was caused by subplantar injection of 0.1 ml of 1% carrageenin solution into the hind leg of rats. The studied substances were administered orally at a dose of 8 mg/kg an hour before the administration of carrageenan. The severity of the inflammatory reaction was assessed 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 24 hours after the induction of inflammation by changing the volume of the paw (oncometrically). Edema was expressed as a percentage of the initial volume of the paws before the introduction of phlogogens. The activity of the studied extracts was determined by their ability to reduce the development of edema compared to the control, and expressed as a percentage, which reflected the degree of inhibition of edema development by this substance in relation to the control, where the amount of edema was taken as 100% ($A = 100\% - (V_{oo} - V_{zo}) * 100 / (V_{ok} - V_{zk})$) [8, 9].

Figure 1. Mixed ligand complex of diclofenac with Ni(II) and ethylenediamin (EDA)

Figure 2. Mixed ligand complex of diclofenac with Zn (II) and ethylenediamin (EDA)

Results and its discussion. The results of the studies are presented in Table 1. As can be seen from the above data, in the control group of rats, the maximum swelling of the paws developed after 3 hours, and

amounted to $162,5 \times 14,8\%$ relative to the outcome, and even after 24 hours it remained significantly elevated by $25 \pm 1,8\%$. The maximum edema in experimental rats taking the studied compounds also occurred 3 hours after administration of carrageenan. At the same time, the effect of these samples, after 24 hours, almost approached the norm. After 3 hours, diclofenac at a dose of 8 mg/kg reduced rat paw edema to $52 \pm 3,8\%$ or 3 times in relation to the control group of animals, MEA to $88,9 \pm 7,7\%$ or 1,8 times, metal salts by 60% or 2,7 times, and new compounds based on them Dicl+Ni(CH₃COO)₂*4H₂O+EDA up to $41,7 \pm 2,8\%$ or 3,9 times, Dicl+Cu(CH₃COO)₂+EDA up to $71,4 \pm 6,6\%$ or 2,3 times and Dicl+Zn(CH₃COO)₂+EDA up to $60 \pm 5,6\%$ or 2,7 times.

Table 1

Effect of coordination compounds based on diclofenac, metal complexes (Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺) and monoethanolamine on the course of carrageenan edema in rats (increase in limb volume in % relative to the initial, $M \pm m$; n=5)

Samples of metal complexes	Time since the introduction of carrageenan, hours					
	1	2	3	4	5	24
Control	87,5±7,2	112,5±10	162,5±14,8	150±13,5	131,3±12,0	25±1,8
Dicl	20±1,6	32±2,2	52±3,8	36±1,5	20±1,6	4±0,3
MEA	44,4±3,8	66,7±5,2	88,9±7,7	66,7±5,9	44,4±3,6	11,1±1,0
EDA	40,0±3,5	61,0±5,0	93,5±7,8	69,0±5,5	40,0±3,2	18±1,4
Ni (CH ₃ COO) ₂	20±1,5	45±3,6	60±5,4	40±1,8	30±2,8	10±0,9
Dicl+Ni(CH ₃ COO) ₂ +EDA	16,8±1,3	29±2,0	41,7±2,8	25±1,0	16,66±1,3	4±0,3
Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂	25±2,0	45±3,5	60±5,3	40±1,9	35±3,2	20±1,5
Dicl+Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂ +EDA	28,5±2,4	52,4±3,9	71,4±6,6	42,85±2,9	33,33±3,0	42,8±2,9
Zn(CH ₃ COO) ₂	18,2±1,4	31,8±2,1	54,5±4,2	40,9±2,1	27,3±2,5	4,5±0,4
Dicl+Zn(CH ₃ COO) ₂ +EDA	25±2,1	40±3,0	60±5,6	40±2,0	25±2,0	10±0,9

diclofenac, metal complexes (Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺) and monoethanolamine relative to control (M±m; n=5)

From the data given in Table 2, it can be seen that the anti-inflammatory effect in all the studied drugs except MEA (38,5%), EDA (33,0%) and Dicl+Cu(CH₃COO)₂+EDA (42,3%) varies between 50-60%.

Table 2

Maximum rat paw growth and anti-inflammatory activity of coordination compounds based on

Samples of metal complexes	The increase in the volume of the foot 3 hours after induction, %	Anti-inflammatory effect, %	p
Control	162,5±14,8	0	-
Dicl	52±3,8	50±4,2	<0,01
MEA	88,9±7,6	38,5±2,6	<0,01
EDA	93,5±7,8	33,0±2,4	-
Ni(CH ₃ COO) ₂	60±5,4	54±4,4	<0,01
Dicl+Ni(CH ₃ COO) ₂ +EDA	41,67±2,8	62±5,5	<0,01
Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂	60±5,4	54±4,3	<0,01
Dicl+Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂ +EDA	71,42±6,6	42,3±3,6	<0,01
Zn(CH ₃ COO) ₂	54,54±4,2	54±4,5	<0,01
Dicl+Zn(CH ₃ COO) ₂ +EDA	60±5,6	54±4,6	<0,01

* p<0.01-confidence in relation to the control.

Conclusion.

The study of the specific anti-inflammatory activity of new diclofenac-based complexes showed that diclofenac, metal complexes (Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺) based on it had antiexudative activity similar in its effectiveness. According to the results obtained, these metal complexes exhibit an anti-inflammatory effect, which decreases in the following order: Dicl-Ni-EDA > Dicl-Zn-EDA > H-Dicl > Dicl-Cu-EDA. The formation of the Dicl-Ni-EDA complex makes it

possible to enhance anti-inflammatory activity.

Acknowledgments. This work was supported by a grant VA-FA-F7-004 from the Coordinating Committee for Development of Science and Technology under the Ministry of Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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